

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Indian Sandalwood Oil's Ability to Shield Against the Negative Effects of Sunlight Exposure

Kiran Pawar*, Sayyed Kirmani, Rajendra kawade

Nandkumar shind college of pharmacy, vaijapur, 423701.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 03 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging activities, anti-inflammatory qualities, antioxidant effects of sandalwood oil, wrinkles and skin aging

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14262220

ABSTRACT

Throughout history, sandalwood oil has been used for many different things, including food, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. Its effects on wrinkled skin are now becoming more widely acknowledged in this review article, a succinct analysis of several skin conditions, particularly skin aging and appearance, has been discussed and wrinkly skin, as well as an explanation of sandalwood oil and how to apply it topically to the skin. Consequently, it emphasizes the use of sandalwood oil's anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties for therapeutic purpose Is to explain the cell-regulating qualities and nitric oxide (NO) scavenging actions on wrinkled skin.

INTRODUCTION

Skin aging is a component of the “aging mosaic” that occurs naturally in humans and takes different forms over time in various organs, tissues, and cells. As the Internal organ aging symptoms are hidden from the ambient “eyes,” the skin makes the first noticeable traces of the time that is passing. It is commonly known that the first factor influencing a person’s sociocultural relationships is their skin our outward appearance plays a critical role in our ability to accept and For societal interactions. Emotions are expressed through the skin. And the manifestation of one’s state of

wellness and health. The signal is produced by the color, opacity, and hydration levels Regarding the psychophysical state. The crease is a groove on The surface of the skin. It results from a gradual loss of collagen resulting in the tissue’s low elasticity and a lower cell division. There are two types of aging that can be discussed in relation to our skin: environmental and chronological aging. From a clinical, historical, and environmental perspective Skin changes associated with ageing include thinning and loss of flexibility, texture, wrinkling, elevated desiccation, and deterioration of the skin’s protective layer. Ageing according to

***Corresponding Author:** Kiran Pawar

Address: Nandkumar shind college of pharmacy, vaijapur, 423701.

Email ✉: kp042019@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

time depends on a reduction in the rate of cell division the epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis (senescence), however, from Deterioration in the Remodeling of the extracellular matrix, such as elastic and collagen bundles. Skin aging in its second form is mediated by external elements like UV rays air pollution, smoking, variations in the outside temperature, and additional agents of exposure skin aging. Popularly referred to as Indian Sandalwood, *Santalum album* L. (*Santalaceae*) is one of the most valuable and ancient natural fragrance sources, possessing immense medicinal and The album S. has gained commercial significance. India, respected worldwide for the last 25 centuries, for its delicious, durable, and therapeutic properties aromatic oil. The derived essential oil from sandalwood various applications of sandal heartwood ancient medical practices, such as Siddha and Ayurveda additionally, Unani medicine in the management and avoidance of numerous illnesses. The flexible medicinal and One reason sandalwood is important for healthcare is because especially abundant source of phytochemicals Sesquiterpenes. plant's heartwood is where sandalwood oil is The extracted. With a variety of minor components, this volatile oil

contains approximately 90% alpha- and beta-santalols 6% or so of sesquiterpene hydrocarbons are included. As the The pleasant smell of is caused by santalols. Sandalwood, while 2-furfuryl pyrrole might produce a result. Approximately 50% of an dark red, set, viscous oil, Stearolic acid is present in this oil along with santalbic acid. Fingerprinting of gas chromatography Given that the components of sandalwood oils are complex, they have been used with success. Sandalwood is primarily used as a sedative and coolant. Effect and astringent properties, which make it beneficial as genitourinary and bronchial tract disinfectant, stimulant, expectorant, and diuretic. The charming and strong and enduring scent renders sandalwood oil beneficial in industry of perfumes. Additionally, it serves as a tonic for memory, anti-poison, liver, stomach, and heart Enhancement as well as a blood cleanser. Multiple applications of the Ayurvedic system makes reference to sandalwood treatment of a number of other illnesses, such as diarrhea, with intrinsic bleeding hemorrhage vomiting, bleeding piles, poisoning, first stage of the pox, hiccoughs, urticaria, and eye inflammation and infections in the umbilicus.

- **What is skin aging?**

Skin aging is primarily caused by two processes: extrinsic and intrinsic. A stochastic mechanism that suggests random damage to cells due to mutations during metabolic activities as a result of the creation of free radicals are also involved. The cause of extrinsic aging is environmental elements like air quality and sun exposure poor nutrition, alcohol abuse, smoking, and pollution. Ageing from within is a reflection of one's genetic makeup and is contingent upon time. Different manifestations of natural aging consist of thin, silky skin and pronounced lines of expression. Skin that is externally aged is characterized by photodamage, such as wrinkles, spots of pigmentation, and uneven actinic keratoses and hypopigmentation. Prompt safeguards such as chemical and physical sunscreens, In addition to limiting your exposure to strong UV radiation, The most crucial thing

- **Changes in skin appearance:**
- **Dry skin:** In elderly people, dry, scaly skin is common. This is partially due to the deterioration or loss of skin barrier function with advancing age. Manifestation the restoration of the compromised barrier Has been shown to occur more slowly in older skin. Increasing the likelihood of dryness developing. This is a complex process that has lower lipid levels as one of its causes a drop in epidermal growth factor levels and lamellar body Filaggrin. Trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL) increased Is also demonstrated by aging skin, which exits the stratum Corneum more prone to drying out
- **Benign neoplasms in ageing skin :** Age-related changes in the skin's surface texture and appearance can be seen in the emergence of seborrheic keratosis, cherry angiomas, and acrochordons, or skin tags. Sun spots, sebaceous cysts, and lentigos among other cutaneous lesions and hyperplasias Changes. Dermatologists' and plastic surgeons' patients Surgeons frequently ask that these benign tumors.

Numerous harmful therapeutic approaches are available, such as sundry laser and hyfreccation alternatives

- **Wrinkles classification:** Wrinkles are classified as:

- **Texture:** Even an infant's skin has a surface pattern made up of grooves or depressions that meet to form a tiny rhomboid area.

- **Expressional:** These are the lines that appear on the face when the skin has to adjust to the movements of the muscles in the face. It is true that the insertion of the facial muscles occurs beneath the skin. As a result, the skin moves in tandem with them. These thirty years old, cranes are visible, but they do not growth in quantity over time; rather, they grow more profound their path is not parallel to the direction of muscle fibers.

- **Joint lines :** They are essential to the skin's natural movements and are situated in the scheletic articulations.

- **Grooves from muscular skin laxity:** They typically manifest as a byproduct of aging, as the collagen texture becomes less elastic. Consequently, the dermis can no longer contrast the gravity and the There is less muscle tissue. This type of groove manifests typically on the face as the skin's natural inclination. In this case, there is only surgical treatment.

- **Lines from sleeping:** When you sleep, these folds are formed from your lateral position. They emerge later on the skin damaged photo.

- **How Wrinkles develop:** The skin is composed of many layers of cells that undergo self-shedding and regeneration in cycles that repeat roughly every 30 days. The tiers can be split roughly into two parts: the upper epidermis and the dermis underneath it. Histological investigations of the skin reveal that a sequence of significant cellular alterations precedes the formation of a wrinkle Cell turnover and regeneration slow down gradually and progressively during the sub-clinical phase of aging (aged 35–45). As a result, the skin

becomes less thick. Consequently, the typically wavy ridge-like DEI, or the dermal-epidermal interface, flattens. The surface area of nutritional exchange is decreased by flatness between the bottom dermis and the underlying dermis top layer of the epidermis. Such free radicals can build up inside of cells and cause unfavorable mutational damage to the cell. Finally, cancer. In the DEI, the adhesion between is typically provided by Collagen IV (basal layer or multi-sheet structure) additionally Collagen VII (fixed to the structure of the sheets). The gradual depletion of nutrients in this region slows the messengers' dissemination, which helps to advance the neo-synthesis process of such collagen. A vicious cycle is set up. Without an optimal amount of collagen, the skin sags even more, propagating the dearth of nutrients. Ironically, the body uses the extra elastin found in mature, aging skin to fill in spaces left by the lack of collagen. Unfortunately, this kind of elastin is broken up, calcified, and overly lipid-rich. Apart from the reduction in skin thickness brought on by insufficient collagen to support it, aging skin is looser and less flexible. These two characteristics are distinctive to furrows.

- **Skin Anti-aging Approaches:**

Here are some approaches to skin anti-aging:

- **Sun protection:**

Avoid the sun, or use sunscreen to block UV radiation. You can also use self-tanner instead of getting a tan.

- **Diet and supplements:**

Eat a healthy, balanced diet, and consider taking supplements that contain vitamins C and E, zinc, and omega-3 fatty acids.

- **Lifestyle:**

Avoid smoking, drink less alcohol, and exercise regularly. Avoid yo-yo dieting, and try to maintain a healthy weight.

- **Topical treatments:**

Use topical treatments that are in sync with your skin's circadian rhythm.

- **Medical treatments:**

A dermatologist can recommend medical treatments like prescription creams, serums, injections, chemical peels, microneedling, and laser treatments.

- **Other approaches:**

Consider retinoids, antioxidants, and natural products like polyphenols. You can also explore alternative compounds for sun protection.

- **Sandalwood plant description :**

The plant was mostly used for steam distillation to produce fragrant sandalwood oil. A small, glabrous, evergreen tree with thin, drooping branches that has white, odorless sapwood. The heartwood has a strong, yellowish brown scent. Petioles are 1–1.3 cm long, slender flowers, brownish purple indurous, in terminal and auxiliary panicle cymes shorter than leaves. Leaves measure 3.8–6.3 by 1.6–3.2 cm; they are elliptic lanceolate, subacute glabrous, and entire thin base acute. Four perianth campanulate limbs, four valvate triangular segments, four exerted stamens, and four rounded, obtuse scales alternate. 1.3 cm diameter globose drupe. Purple-black; endocarp hard, ribbed fruit hidden, roughly pea-sized; spherical, crowned by rim resembling remnants of perianth tube; smooth, somewhat fleshy, almost black; single seed

- **Examining the phytochemistry of sandalwood oil:**

Colorless, the volatile oil that is extracted from the roots and heartwood of *Santalum album* L viscous, yellowish (ref. index: 1.499-1.506, specific Liquid with (gravity 0.962-0.985 opt, rotation -19-200) unusually strong, sweet scent, the main ingredients of the Oil is 90% or more santalol, a blend of two main C₁₅H₂₄O sesquiterpene alcohols, such as α -santalol In the case of 1661670C and β -santalol (b.p-177-1780C), the Most common is the α -form. Above a hundred Tannin classes represented by the components of sandalwood oil .It has been reported that terpenes, resins, and waxes such as the hydrocarbon santene

(C₉H₁₄), α - and β -santalenes, as well as nortricyclo-ekasantalene (C₁₁H₁₈), (C₁₅H₂₄), teresantalol (C₉H₁₆O), and alcohols-santenol Aldehydes-nor-tricyclo-kasantalal (C₁₀H₁₆O), C₁₁H₁₆O.

• **Sandalwood oil restores and rejuvenation of skin aging & wrinkle skin by the following ways:**

1. Antioxidant Properties :

Antioxidant principles that support their traditional medicinal uses were demonstrated by the phytochemical and pharmacological studies. It has been reported to possess both DPPH antioxidant activity and nitrous oxide scavenging activity. The antioxidant and nutritional significance of *S. album*'s anthocyanic pigment cyanidin glucoside has been demonstrated. Nine in vitro antioxidant tests were used in a comparative study to demonstrate that callus cells grown in vitro exhibited antioxidant activities comparable to those of sandalwood oil.

2. Assessment of Nitric Oxide Scavenging Capabilities :

The potential regulatory impact of extracts from Indian medicinal plants, such as *S. album*, was investigated on levels of nitric oxide (NO) with sodium nitroprusside as an in vitro donor of NO. The majority of plant extracts showed scavenging on NO that is directly dose dependent and showed a great deal of activity.

3. Anti-inflammatory properties: Use East Indian sandalwood to treat dry skin conditions like eczema because it has anti-inflammatory properties and acts as an emollient to absorb heat and discomfort away from the skin, as well as aid in the production of cells of healthy skin. Itching is relieved by sandalwood oil, and irritation of the skin, and works best in. It is excellent for anti-aging because it relieves dehydrated skin. Skincare, and the toning effects of the astringent action are excellent effect and works wonders for oily skin as well conditions and to stop unsightly skin formation scars as well as to combat dry

eczema. *Santalum album* significantly inhibited the carrageenan-induced paw edema, cotton, demonstrating its anti-inflammatory and antiulcer properties. Pylorus ligation and pellet-induced granuloma caused an ulcer. These results could support the incorporation of this plant into the efficient administration of ulcers and other inflammatory conditions in the conventional system of medication. The in vivo analgesic and in vitro antioxidant and mice's anti-inflammatory properties were demonstrated for sandalwood methanolic extracts.

4. Cell regulatory properties: Sandalwood oil is calming, cooling, and moisturizing when applied topically. It is mostly used for dry skin conditions brought on by moisture loss and skin inflammations. It can help alleviate eczema and psoriasis, as well as to treat acne and oily skin. The Sandalwood's emollient qualities make it beneficial in skin care. Sandalwood oil has calming, cooling properties and hydrating dry skin conditions brought on by dehydration and management of acne and oily skin

5. Metabolic properties: Sandalwood oil has been shown to alter the hepatic enzymes that metabolize xenobiotics in newborn mouse pups after trans-mammary exposure. It is additionally noted that sandalwood oil and its components altered the hepatic xenobiotic after passing through milk. Metabolizing enzymes, including elevated liver Glutathione reductase, glutathione-S-transferase, and activities of glutathione peroxidase, with accompanying rise in acid-soluble hepatic cytochrome b5 Sulphydryl levels and hepatic cytochrome decline content for P 450.

• **Techniques for applying sandalwood oil:**

- Add one or two drops of sandalwood oil to a large bowl of steaming water to help reduce wrinkles on your face. Cover your head and keep your face over the bowl ten minutes by a towel.
- Apply a few drops of sandalwood oil to each body part.

- Apply a few drops of sandalwood oil to your hair to make it silky and hydrated again.
- You can add sandalwood oil to your bath water to promote better sleep and relaxation.
- To your milk, add a few drops of sandalwood oil energize yourself.
- To lotion, add a few drops of sandalwood oil or cream to get rid of itchy, dry skin.
- A few drops of sandalwood oil can be added to coconut oil
- Apply your other preferred oil to your hair to aid in dryness.
- Applying sandalwood to the skin can help you relax.

CONCLUSIONS:

Depending on their composition, topical applications of sandalwood oil may affect the skin differently. The ingredients in sandalwood oil could rejuvenate and repair wrinkled skin by a number of mechanisms: properties that reduce inflammation; (ii) properties that scavenge nitric oxide (NO); (iv) properties that regulate cells; and (v) properties that affect metabolism. Sandalwood oil can be better understood through additional research, which could lead to the creation of skin care products and dermatological treatments..

REFERENCES

1. Draelos ZD and Pugliese PT. *Physiology of the Skin*. Allured Publishing Corporation, 2011
2. Vierkotter A and Krutmann J. Environmental Influences on skin aging and ethnic-specific Manifestations. *Dermatoendocrinology*, 2012; 4:227–231
3. Ganceviciene R, Liakou IL, Theodoridis A, Makrantonaki E, Zouboulis CC. Skin anti-aging Strategies. *Dermato-endocrinology, Landes Bioscience*, July–December, 2012; 4(3): 308–319.
4. Fisher GJ, Kang S, Varani J, Bata-Csorgo Z, Wan Y, Datta S, Voorhees JJ. Mechanisms of photoaging and chronological skin aging. *Arch. Dermatol*, 2002; 138: 1462–1470.
5. Marrot L. Pollution and Sun Exposure: A Deleterious Synergy. Mechanisms and Opportunities for Skin Protection. *Curr. Med. Chem*, 2017.
6. Kumar R, Anjum N, Tripathi YC. Phytochemistry and Pharmacology of *Santalum Album L.*: A Review. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2015; 4(10): 1842-1876.
7. Benencia F, Courreges MC. Antiviral Activity of Sandalwood oil against Herpes Simplex Viruses 1 & 2. *Phytomedicine*, 1999; 6(2): 119-123.
8. Desai VB, Hiremath RD, Rasal VP, Gaikwad DN, Shankarnarayana KH. Pharmacological Screening of HESP and Sandalwood oil, *Indian Perfumer*, 1991; 35(2): 69-70.
9. Puizina-Ivic N. Skin aging. *Acta Dermatoven APA*, 2008; 17(2).
10. Baumann L. Skin ageing and its treatment. *J Pathol*, 2007; 211: 241–251. DOI: 10.1002/path.2098.
11. Ligman AM, Zheng P, Lavker RM. The anatomy and pathogenesis of wrinkles. *Br. J. Dermatol*, 1985; 113, 37–42. Doi:10.1111/j.1365- 2133.1985.tb02042.x
12. Lam M, Sulindro M. Aging Skin. *Academy of Anti-aging Research*, www.a3r.org. MMIII, No. 1
13. Ganceviciene R, Liakou AI, Theodoridis A, Makrantonaki E, Zouboulis CC. Skin anti-aging Strategies. *Dermato-endocrinology. Landes Bioscience*, 2012; 4(3): 308–319
14. Kirtikar KR, Basu. *Indian Medicinal Plants*, II Ed.(Basu, L/ M. 49, Leader Rd. Allahabad), 1933; 3: 2184–88
15. Brunke EJ. Cyclosantal and Epicyclosantalal a new Sesquiterpene aldehyde from East Indian Sandalwood oil, *Flavour & Fragrance Journal*, 1995;10: 211-219.

16. Scartezzini P, Speroni E. Review on some plants of Indian traditional medicine with antioxidant activity. *J. Ethnopharmacol*, 2000; 71: 23-43
17. Patrick LO, Timothy J. Antioxidants in medicines And spices as cardioprotective agents in Tibetan Highlanders. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 2002; 40: 346-357.
18. Pedapati SHS, Khan MI, Prabhakar P, Giridhar P. Cyanidin-3-glucoside, nutritionally important Constituents and in vitro antioxidant activities of Santalum album L. berries. *Food Research International*, 2012; DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2012.10.024>.
19. Misra BB, Dey S. Phytochemical analyses and Evaluation of antioxidant efficacy of in vitro callus Extract of East Indian Sandalwood Tree (*Santalum Album L.*). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 2012; 1(8): 18.
20. Banerjee S, Ecavade A, Rao AR. Modulatory Influence of sandalwood oil on mouse hepatic Glutathione S-transferase activity and acid soluble Sulphydryl level. *Cancer Letters*, 1993; 68: 105-109.
21. Misra BB, Dey S. Evaluation of in vivo anti-Hyperglycemic and antioxidant potentials of α -Santalol and sandalwood oil. *Phytomedicine*, 2013; 20: 409-416.
22. Jagetia GC, Baliga MS. Evaluation of Nitric Oxide Scavenging activity of certain Indian medicinal Plants in-vitro: a preliminary study. *J Med Food*, 2004; 7: 343-348.
23. Saneja A, Kaushik P, Kaushik D, Kumar S, Kumar .D. Antioxidant, analgesic and antiinflammatory Activities of Santalum album Linn. *Planta Medica*, 2009; 75: 102.
24. Mojay G. Aromatherapy for healing the spirit: Restoring Emotional and Mental Balance with Essential Oils.
25. Davis P, Aromatherapy: An A-Z. 2nd edn. The C.W. Daniel Company Limited, Great Britain, 1999; as cited in Battaglia 2007.
26. Lawless J, The encyclopedias of essential oils, 1992; as cited in Battaglia, 2007.
27. Chaabra SK, Rao AR, Postnatal modulation of Xenobiotic 417 metabolizing enzymes in liver of mouse pups following transactional exposure to Sandalwood oil. *Nutrition Research*, 1993; 13: 1191-1202

HOW TO CITE: Kiran Pawar*, Sayyed Kirmani, Rajendra kawade, Indian Sandalwood Oil's Ability to Shield Against the Negative Effects of Sunlight Exposure, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 187-194. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14262220>